

Original Article

Synthesis, Characterization and Antimicrobial Activity of Polyacetal/Chitosan Nanoparticles Polymer Blend

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Polyacetal was synthesized from the reaction of PVA with p-bromobenzaldehyde. Polymer blend with Nano Chitosan was prepared through the technique of solution casting method. All prepared compounds have been characterized through FT-IR, DSC-TGA, SEM, as well as the *Biological activity*. The FT-IR results indicates the formation of polyacetal. The DSC results indicates the thermal stability regarding prepared polymer blends. Antibacterial potential related to synthesized polyacetal and Nano chitosan blend against four types of bacteria namely *Staphylococcus aureas*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* were examined and evaluated. The results reveal that the prepared polymer blends have good antibacterial activity against all kinds of bacteria.

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Introduction

Polymeric materials are commonly used in biomedical applications. Natural polymers are also necessary in the biomedical area due to their biocompatibility and biodegradability, despite the fact that synthetic polymers are considerably easier to utilize. Blending synthetic and natural polymers is another way to make polymeric materials for biological purposes. During the last three decades, there has been a growing attention in novel materials based on blending of two or more polymers. When compared to single components, blending of natural and synthetic polymers can produce a new material with enhanced mechanical characteristics and biocompatible. Bioartificial or biosynthetic polymeric materials have been coined to describe them [1-4]. Synthetic polymers can include a remnant of impurities like initiators which will prevent the growth of cells. Polymers from natural origin are typically have biocompatibility [5,6]. Synthetic polymers outperform numerous naturally occurring polymers in terms of mechanical characteristics and thermal stability. Several natural polymers also have performance limitations when compared to manmade polymers. Synthetic polymers may be treated into a variety of forms, but natural polymers can only be processed into a limited number of shapes. For example, high temperatures applied during processing

can damage the original structure of natural polymers. Newly discovered polymeric materials made up of a mix of natural and synthetic polymers should be biocompatible while also having acceptable thermal and mechanical characteristics for usage in biomedical applications [7].

Last decades polyacetals have been synthesized, their diverse physicochemical characteristics have led to their use in a number of disciplines, including catalysis [8], photochemistry [9], electrochemistry [10], material science [11], protein crystallography [12,13] and medicine [14]. Polyacetals have a lot of potential in biological applications since nearly every aspect that influences its interaction with target biological macromolecules may be changed to improve their positive effects on the biological system [15-18]. With focused and repeatable synthetic methods, tailor-made systems of POM, including organic-inorganic hybrids and nanocomposites, with improved biological characteristics are now conceivable [19-26]. Chermann et al. identified the inhibitory action of silicotungstic acid on murine leukaemia and sarcoma viruses in 1970, laying the groundwork for the study of physiologically active POMs [27]. This prompted extensive research into the antiviral effects of polyacetals, which revealed that inhibition of enzymes (for example, reverse transcriptase HIV inactivation) which plays a key role in their action [28-30]. As a result, new biological activities were found, such as the insulin-mimetic action of POMs in the treatment of diabetes [31-34], anticancer [35,36] and antibiotic [37]. Decavanadate's antiparasitic properties and anti-leishmanial activity [38].

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Figure 1: Preparation reaction of polyacetal

The modified chitosan has sparked a lot of attention, particularly because of its bactericidal properties against a variety of microorganisms [39]. Composites with (nanoparticles, nanomaterials) are foreseen to be more effective on bacteria by disrupting and penetrating its cell membranes owing to their high ratio aspect and surface area. Bulk materials' physical characteristics can be improved by nanoscale materials [40].

Material and Methods

Preparation of poly vinyl alcohol acetal [41]

PVA (1.5gm) has been dissolved in (25ml) DMSO at a temperature of (50°C) and added with mixing, the solution has been mixed in (250ml) round bottle (benzene) with two drops of HCl, (1.2 g/1mmole) of (p-bromobenzaldehyde) was added to solution, and after that stirred magnetically at a temperature of (50°C) for 24hrs,

by adding a few drops of (5N) NaOH solution to the resultant combination was neutralized. The crude product washed with acetone and distilled water many times. The product has been dried at a temperature of (40°C) for a period of 12 hrs. Synthetic route related to target compounds can be seen in figure 1.

Polymer blend preparation

Polymer blend films have been prepared through solution casting method. Polyacetal solution have been prepared through dissolving the polyacetal in H₂O at a temperature of (50°C) with stirring. Nano chitosan has been dissolved in 2% acetic acid with stirring at room temperature to create (5%) polymer solution. The two polymer solutions (PA and NanoCh) have been mixed at different ratios to obtain three blends B1, B2 and B3 with percentage ratios of 25:75, 50:50 and 75:25 respectively.

Results

PVAcyclicacetal (PA) was prepared from the reaction of PVA with p-bromobenzaldehyde, (FTIR) spectrum for (PA), indicates bands at (3471cm⁻¹) due to (O-H stretching vibration), (2889cm⁻¹) regarding (C-H symmetric stretching), also (1111cm⁻¹) duo to (C-O-H stretching). Bands at (3100) cm⁻¹ due to (C-H aromatic stretching), (1662) cm⁻¹ due to (C=C aromatic) (1342cm⁻¹) and (C-O) acetal group of (PA) at (1153 cm⁻¹). FT-IR spectrum regarding blend polymers showed a broad absorption band in range 3442cm⁻¹ corresponding to (N-H and O-H stretching vibration), 2918cm⁻¹ is due to (C-H symmetric stretch), (1639cm⁻¹) due to (C=C aromatic) (1415cm⁻¹), (C-O) acetal group of (PA) at (1147cm⁻¹) and (1105cm⁻¹) due to (C-O-H stretching).

Thermo gravimetric (DSC- TGA) for the pure PVA and PA/Nano Ch polymer blend has been measured at temperatures in range of (0 up to 600°C) with 10°C/min constant rate. The TGA curve that is related to PVA indicates 3 steps regarding continuous mass loss. The initial step is at (340.67°C) with (-48.13%) mass loss regarding

Figure 2: a) Thermal analysis of PVA and b) PA-Nano Chitosan

Figure 3a: The SEM images of polymer blend B1

Figure 3b: The SEM images of polymer blend B3

the volatile compounds. The second step is (340.67-435.96°C) with (-14.07%) mass loss and the final step is (435.96-594.67°C) (decomposition regarding polymer's side chain) as well as weight loss of approximately (-22.37%). DSC curve in figure 2a for the PVA indicated glass transition temperature T_g at a temperature of (68.4°C). Endothermic peak at a temperature of (214.5°C) related to polymer melting T_m . Degradation temperature T_d at a temperature of (454.9°C).

TGA thermo gram regarding the blend (PA/Nano Ch) indicates one step of weight loss at (595.9°C) with the weight loss approximately (-62.77%). DSC curve related to blend (PA/Nano Ch) show glass transition temperature T_g at a temperature of (112.2°C). Endothermic peak related to melting temperature point T_m at a temperature of (269°C). It was observed that the blend film show only one T_g on its thermogram. This indicates the presence of hydrogen bonding interactions between PA and Nano Ch polymer blend and that the two polymers are well blended together.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is a powerful tool for visualizing surface morphology and determining the physical condition of a surface. Figures 3a and 3b show the surface morphology and cross sectional morphology of a binary mix of polyacetal and nano chitosan as determined by SEM investigations. The presence of nano chitosan is noticed to be with homogenous

spherical distribution on the surface of the matrix with average size 22-43nm for nano chitosan particles. The higher NanoCh content, the denser the structure in the blend B1 as in figure 3a. The PA/Ch blend B3 has exhibited a dense microstructure as illustrated in figure 3b.

Discussion

The synthesized polyacetal and PA/Nano Ch blend have been evaluated *in vitro* against bacteria: *Bacillus subtilis*, *E-coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

Results related to anti-bacterial activity indicate that all of the prepared blends showed a good activity against all bacteria types. Increasing the biological activities with increasing the percentage of NanoCh is because of the impact regarding nano chitosan which is Cationic polyelectrolytes and like many molecules with positive charge that have capability of killing microorganisms [42]. Chitosan the polycationic substance that exhibits antimicrobial properties against gram negative and gram positive microorganisms [43]. The binding of cationic sites of chitosan to the anionic surfaces disrupts the microbial cell wall, resulting in cell death [44]. Antimicrobial properties of chitosan nanoparticles have been demonstrated. LiFeng Qi and his coworkers [45]. Nanochitosan was shown to have greater antibacterial activity than chitosan itself. Chitosan nanoparticles have a greater antibacterial activity than chitosan because of their unique properties. The chitosan nanoparticles were effectively dispersed in the bacterial solution, allowing bacteria to attach to the nanochitosan surface in a short period of time, indicating that nanoCh has antimicrobial properties. The bacterial cell negative charge is the target of polycation. Polycationic nanoCh with a higher charge surface density interacts with bacteria more effectively than chitosan. The bacterial cell wall negative surface charge interacts more effectively with the polycationic nanochitosan (NH_3^+), inhibiting the microorganism's development [46]. Due to the NanoCh large surface area, that could be adsorbed tightly to the bacterial cell surface to disrupt the cell membrane, that will lead to intracellular components leakage, which will kill the bacteria, chitosan nanoparticles have a high affinity to the bacteria cells for a quantum-size effect [47,48].

Conclusion

Polyacetal and nano chitosan polymer blend was prepared through solution casting method. Thermal analysis revealed addition of nano chitosan improves thermal stability of PA/nano chitosan blends. Biological activity revealed that the prepared polymer blends have good antibacterial activity against all kinds of bacteria.

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Table 1: Inhibition circle diameter in mm for the polymer blends

Compound	<i>Esherichia Coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Bacillus cerues</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
B1	27	24	25	26
B2	24	20	14	22
B3	25	17	17	24

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